

A Prospective and Retrospective Comparative Study of Free Omental Sheet Graft and Other Operative Procedures of Enteric Perforation RepairSheetanshu Gupta¹, Kamal Bansal², Anil K. Sharma³, Rajesh Chahil²¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, JLN Medical College & Associated Hospitals, Ajmer, Rajasthan²Assistant Professor, Department of General Surgery, JLN Medical College & Associated Hospitals, Ajmer, Rajasthan³Associate Professor, Department of General Surgery, JLN Medical College & Associated Hospitals, Ajmer, Rajasthan

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Abstract:**Background:** Enteric perforation, often caused by infectious diseases like typhoid, is a significant cause of morbidity and mortality in developing countries such as India. Our study aims to compare the outcomes of using a free omental sheet graft versus other operative procedures for enteric perforation repair.**Method:** This study includes both prospective and retrospective comparative analysis. It was conducted on 150 patients admitted to the emergency ward of the Department of General Surgery at J.L.N. Medical College and Associated Group of Hospitals, Ajmer. Patients were randomly assigned to three groups, each consisting of 50 patients: GROUP A - Primary repair with the omental sheet, GROUP B - Primary repair alone, and GROUP C - Resection and anastomosis.**Result:** The rate of fecal fistula formation in each group was as follows: Group C had 6% of patients with fistula formation, Group B had 10%, and Group A had 2%. Regarding mortality, Group C and Group B had approximately 4% mortality each, while Group A had no mortality.**Conclusion:** Simple repair with a free omental sheet graft applied to the perforated site in the affected gut was successful. This approach likely prevents repair leaks, new perforations, and fecal fistulas by covering at least 10 cm of the affected gut. This significantly lowers both morbidity and mortality.**Keywords:** Enteric Perforation, Omental Sheet Graft, Enteric Perforation Repair.

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Introduction

In India, generalized peritonitis resulting from gastrointestinal perforation is a common surgical emergency. Despite advances in perioperative care, antimicrobial therapy, and intensive care support, perforation peritonitis continues to result in high morbidity and mortality.

The terminal portions of the ileum, caecum, and appendix form a critical anatomical region, with various conditions affecting this area, often necessitating surgical intervention. The most common cause of non-traumatic ileal perforation is typhoid fever (Fig. 1), though other factors, such as tuberculosis, nonspecific inflammation, obstruction, radiation enteritis, and Crohn's disease, can also contribute. Laparotomy with primary closure is generally the preferred approach for treating these conditions, depending on the bowel's condition. Efforts to reduce the complications associated with primary closure are ongoing, aiming to lower patient morbidity. One of

the most serious complications after primary closure is the development of fecal fistulas (Fig. 2), which are among the leading causes of death. Many fistulas and abscesses are managed conservatively. Notably, applying the omentum as a patch over the primary closure site significantly reduces the incidence of fecal fistulas. The Graham patch, developed in 1937 by Dr. Roscoe Reid Graham for treating perforated duodenal ulcers, is a well-known example of this technique. This method involves carefully placing a piece of omentum over the perforated area as a definitive treatment.

The mechanism behind omental adhesion involves the formation of a fibrin exudate at the injury site, creating a bridge between the perforation and the surrounding tissue. This fibrin scaffold promotes the migration of leukocytes—particularly macrophages, neutrophils, and fibroblasts—leading to collagen deposition around the injured area. Interestingly, this physiological process also

contributes to the formation of omental adhesions after injury or surgery. From a therapeutic perspective, targeting the cytokines responsible for adhesion formation could potentially offer a new avenue for treatment. While animal studies have shown that wrapping the omentum around an anastomosis can aid in healing, human studies have primarily demonstrated its benefit in upper GI surgery.

There remains debate over whether the use of omentum to reinforce colonic anastomosis reduces the risk of anastomotic leakage. Senn, in the late 1800s, concluded that covering surgical wounds with omentum mimicked nature's method of preventing perforation of the peritoneal cavity and promoting visceral wound healing. Recent advances have enhanced our understanding of the omentum's role, not only as a lymphoid organ but also as a metabolic regulator. It is increasingly recognized for its potential in limiting the spread of

intra-abdominal tumors, and macrophages and B cells from milky spots have shown cytotoxic activity in vitro, potentially opening new avenues for cancer treatment. Furthermore, its characteristics may benefit tissue healing in surgery and could be harnessed in tissue engineering and transplantation. The choice of surgical approach depends on several factors, including the patient's age, overall health, the time between symptom onset and surgery, the degree of peritoneal contamination, the number of perforations, the distance of the perforation from the ileocaecal valve, and the condition of the bowel.

The purpose of this study is to compare the effectiveness of using a free omental sheet graft in perforated typhoid enteritis with other methods of enteric perforation repair, such as primary repair and resection anastomosis, as observed at J.L.N. Medical College and Hospital, Ajmer.

Figure 1: Ileal Perforation

Figure 2: Fecal Fistula

Aims and Objectives

The aim of our study is to prospectively compare the outcomes of using omental sheet grafts with primary closure and other operative methods, such as primary repair and resection-anastomosis, as emergency management techniques for enteric perforation. Specifically, we aim to assess and compare the morbidity, mortality, cost-effectiveness, and complications associated with each of these procedures.

Material and Methods

Source of Data: The data for this study will be collected from a pretested proforma, which includes clinical history, general physical examination, relevant investigations, imaging modalities, and patient follow-up over the study period from March 2020 to March 2022. The study will involve 150 patients selected from inpatients in the emergency ward of the Department of General Surgery, J.L.N. Medical College and Associated Group of Hospitals, Ajmer. Patients will be clinically diagnosed after meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study.

Study Design: Prospective and Retrospective Comparative Study

Setting: The study will be conducted at J.L.N. Medical College and the associated hospitals, with patients selected from inpatients in the emergency ward.

Inclusion Criteria: All patients diagnosed with typhoid fever (Widal or blood culture positive) who present with signs and symptoms of perforation, supported by clinical and radiological findings.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients with perforation associated with any of the following conditions will be excluded:

- a) Malignancy
- b) Tuberculosis (TB)
- c) Trauma
- d) Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD)
- e) Pregnancy
- f) Patients who do not consent to surgery
- g) Previous surgery for intestinal obstruction, pathology, or adhesiolysis
- h) Unviable bowel, where primary repair is not possible, and ileostomy is planned

Investigations:

- Hemoglobin, Total Leukocyte Count (TLC), Differential Leukocyte Count (DLC), Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate (ESR), Bleeding Time (BT), Coagulation Profile (CT)
- Blood sugar, Blood urea, Serum creatinine
- Serum electrolytes
- Chest X-ray (PA view), FPA (standing position)

- Widal test
- Liver function tests

Preoperative Preparation: Each case will be thoroughly investigated and prepared for surgery as follows:

1. Correction of dehydration and electrolyte imbalances.
2. Nil per os (NBM) with Ryle's tube suction and bowel preparation.
3. Administration of broad-spectrum antibiotics.
4. Regular monitoring of pulse, blood pressure (BP), temperature, respiration, input/output charting, and electrolytes.

Intraoperative Procedures: Only patients who meet the criteria for primary closure (single or multiple perforations with relatively healthy bowel) will be included in the study.

- **Group A:** Primary closure will be performed in two layers using interrupted sutures. The inner layer will be sutured with 3-0 Vicryl, while the outer layer will be sutured with 3-0 silk. A free omental sheet will then be brought down and fixed at the perforation site with 3-0 Vicryl, covering the repaired area as a patch.
- **Group B:** Primary closure will be performed similarly to Group A with two layers of interrupted sutures, using 3-0 Vicryl for the inner layer and 3-0 silk for the outer layer, without the application of an omental sheet.
- **Group C:** Resection and anastomosis will be performed for patients with single or multiple perforations and relatively healthy bowel.

In all cases, the abdominal cavity will be irrigated with 5 liters of normal saline, and a single 28F drain will be placed in the pelvis. The abdominal cavity will then be closed.

Postoperative Care:

- Nasogastric suction and intravenous (IV) fluids will be administered until bowel function returns.
- Postoperatively, patients will receive broad-spectrum antibiotics, antacids, antiemetics, analgesics, and other supportive treatments.
- Patients will be monitored for wound infections, wound dehiscence, septicemia, fecal fistula formation, anastomotic leaks, and mortality until discharge. Further follow-up will be conducted for three months.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be entered into an Excel spreadsheet (MS Office Excel) and analyzed using SPSS statistical software (version 23.0.0).

- Quantitative data will be summarized as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), and differences between the mean values of the groups will be analyzed using ANOVA.

- Qualitative data will be summarized as proportions, and the differences between proportions will be analyzed using the Chi-square test.
- A probability value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results:**Table 1: Distribution of Hospital Stay according to Group**

	N	Mean Hospital Stay	Std. Deviation	F Value	P value
Group A	50	5.5000	.86307	5.368	0.006*
Group B	50	5.9000	.86307		
Group C	50	6.0800	.98644		
Total	150	5.8267	.93225		

*Significant; **not significant

Table 2: Distribution of Operative Findings according to study groups

Operative findings	Group A	Group B	Group C	Total	Chi Sq	P value
Gangrenous segment with perforation	0	0	2 (4%)	2 (1.3%)	150.0	<.0001*
Multiple Perforation	0	0	8 (16.0%)	8 (5.3%)		
Single perforation <1cm	50 (100.0%)	50 (100.0%)	0	100 (66.7%)		
Single perforation >1cm	0	0	40 (80.0%)	40 (26.7%)		
Total	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	150 (100%)		

*Significant; **not significant

Table 3: Distribution of Fecal fistula according to Group

		Group			Total	Chi sq	P value
		Group A	Group B	Group C			
Fecal Fistula	No	49(98.0%)	45(90.0%)	47(94.0%)	141(94.0%)	2.8377	0.242**
	Yes	1 (2.0%)	5 (10.0%)	3 (6.0%)	9 (6.0%)		
Total		50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	150(100.0%)		

*Significant; **not significant

Table 4: Distribution of Mortality according to Group

		Group			Total	Chi sq	P value
		Group A	Group B	Group C			
Mortality	No	50 (100.0%)	48(96.0%)	48(96.0%)	146(97.3%)	2.055	0.358**
	Yes	0 (0%)	2(4.0%)	2(4.0%)	4(2.7%)		
Total		50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	150(100.0%)		

*Significant; **not significant

Table 5: Distribution of Septicemia according to Group

		Group			Total	Chi sq	P value
		Group A	Group B	Group C			
Septicemia	No	49(98.0%)	47(94.0%)	43(86.0%)	139(92.7%)	5.492	0.064**
	Yes	1(2.0%)	3(6.0%)	7(14.0%)	11(7.3%)		
Total		50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	50(100.0%)	150(100.0%)		

*Significant; **not significant

Discussion

In the Indian subcontinent, typhoid fever, caused by the gram-negative bacterium *Salmonella typhi*, is endemic and a leading cause of enteric perforation. Intestinal perforation is one of the most severe complications of enteric fever in developing countries, often leading to diffuse peritonitis dominantly affects young males in their prime years of economic productivity.

Patients with enteric perforation face several critical issues, including generalized peritonitis, sepsis, dehydration, and disturbances in fluid-

electrolyte and acid-base balance. These complications are further exacerbated in patients who have received home treatment for typhoid fever, as the development of abdominal symptoms is often misinterpreted, and perforation signs are overlooked due to the false sense of security provided by antibiotics. It is crucial to correct fluid-electrolyte imbalances and administer blood transfusions when necessary. The most commonly recommended antibiotics are combinations of chloramphenicol, aminoglycosides, and metronidazole. Successful management requires surgery, appropriate antibiotic therapy, electrolyte

correction, and adequate resuscitation. However, early surgical intervention remains effective treatment. The primary goals of surgery are to close the perforation and perform thorough peritoneal lavage with an antiseptic solution, such as a povidone-iodine-saline mix.

Although some studies consider peritoneal drains unnecessary, our experience suggests that in over 75% of patients, the drainage tubes continue to drain for 12 hours or longer. Typically, the tubes can be removed 24 hours after drainage has ceased.

Postoperative complications not only prolong the patients sufferings but also increase their length of stay in the hospital, thereby escalating both the hospital's and the patient's financial burden.

In our study, we compared the outcomes of three groups: primary closure with an omental patch (Group A), primary closure alone (Group B), and resection-anastomosis (Group C). We found that patients who received primary closure with an omental patch had the lowest rate of perforation leaks. Fistula formation, which commonly follows primary closure of a perforation, was seen in 10% of patients in Group B, the highest rate in our study. In Group C, 6% developed fistulas, while in Group A, only 2% had fistula formation. This finding is consistent with those of Karmacharya and Sharma et al.

To reduce the incidence of fistulas and associated morbidity and mortality, we introduced the "free omental sheet graft" technique, where the omentum was used to cover at least 10 cm of the diseased ileum, including the areas with impending perforation, on either side of the repaired perforation. This was combined with peritoneal toilet and drainage. When compared with primary closure alone (Group B) and resection-anastomosis (Group C), Group A showed a significantly lower rate of complications.

Re-perforation or multiple perforations can lead to the formation of fecal fistulas. The choice of surgery depends on several factors, such as the location, size, and number of perforations, as well as the condition of the gut and the patient's overall health.

In cases with a single perforation (<1 cm), primary repair with omental patching was performed. For larger perforations (>1 cm), multiple perforations, or gangrenous bowel segments, resection-anastomosis was chosen.

In Group B, five patients who underwent primary closure developed fecal fistulas. Four of these

patients were managed conservatively, and one was re-explored, revealing no leak at the repair site but a new perforation. This was subsequently repaired with an ileo-transverse bypass. In Group C, three patients developed fecal fistulas, with two managed conservatively and one requiring surgery. Multiple perforations were found near the anastomosis, leading to the creation of a diversion stoma due to the patient's general condition.

In Group A, one patient developed a fistula that required exploration. No repair leak was found, but a new perforation was noted near the edge of the omental sheet. The omental sheet itself appeared pink, without signs of avascularity, and was densely adherent to the bowel serosa. The repair was adjusted, and an ileo-transverse bypass was performed.

Although some studies suggest that the surgical technique is not directly related to the development of fecal fistulas and mortality, our study showed that the use of a free omental sheet graft significantly reduced the occurrence of both repair leaks and new perforations. The free omental graft effectively prevented further complications, thus lowering both morbidity and mortality.

Our study demonstrated low mortality, with Group B and C showing a mortal around 4%. In Group B, one patient died due to septicemia after developing a fecal fistula, while another patient died from ventilator-acquired pneumonia following surgical exploration. In Group C, one patient died due to septicemia after developing a burst abdomen, and one died due to cachexia, electrolyte imbalances, and toxemia. In contrast, no mortality was observed in Group A.

Intraoperative abscess formation was found only in Group C, likely due to the presence of gangrenous bowel segments or the large size of perforations, which contributed to severe peritonitis.

This may explain why 14% of patients in Group C developed septicemia, compared to 2% in Group A and 6% in Group B.

The early stages of sepsis, characterized by excessive inflammation and sometimes a cytokine storm, may lead to a prolonged period of impaired immune response, delaying healing and potentially resulting in a burst abdomen.

Group C had the highest rate of burst abdomen (8%), followed by Group B (4%), and Group A (2%). All cases of burst abdomen were managed conservatively, except for one in Group C, where the patient died due to septicemia.

Figure 3: Ileal Perforation

Figure 4: Free Omental Graft

Conclusion

Typhoid perforations continue to have high rates of morbidity and mortality, regardless of the surgical method employed. The number of perforations and the development of postoperative fecal fistulas are significant factors that contribute to mortality. The use of free omental sheet grafts is simple, safe, and effective, making it a feasible option for any general surgeon. This procedure does not require specialized training or incur additional costs, making it accessible and practical in various clinical settings. In this study, the combination of simple repair and free omental sheet graft application at the perforated site in the diseased gut proved successful. The omental graft covered at least 10 cm of the surrounding affected gut, effectively addressing impending perforation sites. This approach helps to prevent repair leaks, new perforations, and the formation of fecal fistulas, significantly reducing both morbidity and mortality. Laparotomy with primary closure remains the primary treatment for enteric perforation peritonitis, depending on the condition of the bowel. While the use of omentum in surgery is not new, it has not been strongly emphasized in ileal perforation cases. Recognizing its value in other surgical contexts, we applied the omental patch technique to ileal perforations and found it to be a viable alternative to primary closure alone. Given its clear advantages, we recommend incorporating this technique in all cases of enteric perforation that meet the criteria for primary closure. It is a straightforward procedure that requires minimal additional time and is associated with fewer complications.

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